

PROMOTION AND QUALITY OF SERVICE WITH INTERESTS TO VISIT TOURIST OBJECTS: SISTEMATIC SEARCH

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Abstract

The aim of the research is the systematic search of promotion and quality of service with interest to visit tourist objects. This article is a systematic search that collects data from relevant indexed journals in Indonesia. These findings are discussed in a theoretical study so as to produce a conclusion. This article draws the conclusion that in the current era, the use of the right marketing strategy is very important because many new attractions are emerging as competitors. Applying the right marketing strategy will bring tourists and make tourists who have visited have an interest to visit again. The interest in revisiting is the encouragement of someone to carry out a visit to the destination that was visited. The regional tourism industry pays attention to the duties and functions of the promotion department and service quality in planning and implementing strategies that optimize a tourist interest. The quality of service within these institutions and local governments in the field of tourism is very closely related and has a strong influence on the tourism industry. There are promotion factors and service quality, connected with the interest of the local government in tourists visiting directly or indirectly, thus affecting the development of industries in the region. The attitude of the local government directly influences the visit of domestic and foreign tourists, then indirectly the situation and stable conditions in political, economic and security developments. The contribution of this research is to study theories about promotion and service quality with an interest in visiting tourist objects.

Keywords: promotion, service quality, returning interest, tourists.

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1. Introduction

Nowadays traveling has become a very important trend and human need. Although including secondary needs, this activity is very helpful for someone to get rid of boredom and refresh the mind after facing daily routines. Tourism is a travel activity that is carried out temporarily from the original residence to the destination with the reason not to settle or make a living, but only to fulfill curiosity, spend leisure time and other destinations [1].

The tourism sector is an important economic sector in Indonesia. In 2009, tourism ranked third in terms of foreign exchange earnings after oil and gas commodities and palm oil. According to data from the Indonesian Ministry of Culture and Tourism, in 2010, the number of foreign tourists coming to Indonesia amounted to 7,002,944 people, an increase of 10.74 %, compared to the previous year and contributed the foreign exchange to the country amounting to 7,603.45 million US dollars, whereas the number of archipelago tourists is 122,312,000 people [2].

BPS data from 2013 shows that the international tourism sector contributed 9 % of GDP (Gross Domestic Product) internationally, 1 in 11 vacancies in the tourism sector, 6 % of world exports, and 6 % of exports of poor countries, therefore the tourism sector provides a positive impact on the country that makes the tourism sector a mainstay sector in building its economic strength. Data on state revenue projections of the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy [3], also stated that tourism will be an important revenue sector to beat the oil and gas sector in 2019. The development of tourism activities in an area will have an influence on the economic sector and encourage the development of other sectors, especially in expanding employment and business opportunities. The development of tourism in Indonesia is not far from the marketing activities, carried out by the government and related parties. Marketing is a business effectiveness system, designed to plan, to set prices, to and to distribute products,

services, and ideas that are able to satisfy market desires in order to achieve organizational goals. In marketing activities there are four essential tools, namely: product, place, price, and promotion [4].

In the current era, the use of appropriate marketing strategies in marketing tourism objects is very important because there are currently many new tourism objects emerging as competitors. Applying the right marketing strategy will bring tourists and make tourists who have visited have an interest to visit again.

The interest in revisiting is the encouragement of someone to carry out a visit to the destination that was visited. There are several factors that can influence tourists to visit again, namely service quality, destination image, tourist attraction, and promotion. Promotion and quality of service can be an important factor in influencing the return interest. Promotional activities are various activities, carried out by companies that highlight the features of their products that persuade consumers to buy them. Promotion has the function to create an *image* or impression of what is advertised [5]. The better the promotion, the more interesting it will be for tourists to visit again. Quality of service is an effort to meet the needs and desires of consumers and the accuracy of the delivery method in order to meet the expectations and satisfaction of these customers. The impression of the quality of service, received by tourists, will affect the behavior of tourists who come. The more satisfying quality of service, received by tourists, will attract tourists to visit again.

The aim of the research is the systematic search of promotion and quality of service with interest to visit tourist objects.

2. Material and Method

This article is a systematic search that collects data from relevant indexed journals in Indonesia. These findings are discussed in a theoretical study so as to produce a conclusion.

3. Result

Promotion

Promotional activities are various activities, carried out by companies that highlight the features of their products that persuade consumers to buy them [1,6]. Another definition, promotion is a way to communicate the goods and services offered so that consumers know and buy [2]. The company needs to set promotional goals that will help the achievement of the company's goals more broadly.

Promotional programs can be based on one or more of the following objectives [6]:

1. Provide information. The basic purpose of all promotional activities is to provide potential consumers with information about the products offered, where consumers can buy them, and at what price. Consumers need the information in making their purchasing decisions.

2. Increase sales. Promotional activities are also one way to increase sales. Companies can design sales promotions by providing shopping coupons, product samples, and so on. To persuade consumers to try products offered at lower prices or with additional benefits.

3. Stabilize sales. At the time of sluggish market, companies need to do promotional activities so that the company's sales level does not experience a significant decline.

4. Position the product. Companies need to position their products by emphasizing the superiority of their products, compared to competitors' products. Appropriate promotional strategies, such as *ik lan*, can help the company.

5. Shaping product image. Promotional activities, undertaken by the company, can help consumers image of the products offered. Companies can use advertising media to build product traffics in the eyes of consumers.

The proportional mix consists of two components, namely personal sales activities and non-personal sales activities that are combined by marketers to meet the needs of customers who are the target of the company and to combine their messages effectively and efficiently to them. A promotional mix consists of six variables [7], namely:

1. Advertising: forms of communication that do marketers to inform and persuade the market as well as the target market. Advertising is a promotion that is very well known by the consumer community. Advertising has an open nature and consumers tend to view the advertised product as a standard of the company that conducts the ad. Indicators that characterize the promotion are the reach of the promotion, the quantity of ad serving in the promotional media, and the quality of the delivery of the message in ad serving in the promotional media.

2. Personal selling: communication face to face to promote the goods or services, find sales prospects, and provide after-sales service.

3. Word of mouth promotion: a word of mouth promotion occurs when consumers discuss the value, offered by producers, both negatively and positively.

4. Public relations: a management function which evaluates public attitudes, take measures in accordance with the public interest, and take the necessary measures so that the public can understand and accept the company's products. Nowadays public relations is increasingly important in companies to bridge communication between companies and customers, business relations, government or other external parties.

5. Publicity: all forms of information about individuals, products, organizations that flow to the community through the mass media without paying and outside the control of the sponsor.

6. Sales promotion: sales promotion can be an effective means of promotion, depending on the characteristics of the product. If consumers can be influenced after trying a product, maybe a sales promotion in the form of free distribution of product samples, can be effective. Sales promotion is an attempt to influence consumers and other parties through short-term activities.

Service quality

Service quality is addressing the needs and desires of consumers and accuracy of a delivery method in order to meet the customer's expectations and satisfaction [8]. In good service quality, there are several types of service criteria, including [9]:

1. Timeliness of service, including the time to wait during the transfer of witnesses and the payment process.

2. Service accuracy, namely minimizing errors in services and transactions.

3. Courtesy and friendliness when providing services.

4. Ease of getting services, such as the availability of human resources to help serve consumers, as well as supporting facilities, such as computers to find the availability of a product.

5. Consumer convenience, namely locations, parking lots, comfortable waiting rooms, cleanliness aspects, information availability, and so on.

According to Parasuraman [10], service quality has five dimensions, namely:

a. Tangibles: concrete evidence of a company's ability to show the best for customers, both in terms of the physical appearance of buildings, facilities, supporting technology equipment, to the appearance of employees.

b. Reliability: the company's ability to provide services in accordance with consumer expectations, related to speed, timeliness, no errors, sympathetic attitudes and so on.

c. Responsiveness: responsiveness in providing appropriate or responsive services and accompanied by clear and easy to understand delivery.

d. Assurance: guarantees and certainty, obtained from the attitude of employee courtesy, good communication, and knowledge possessed, so as to be able to foster customer trust.

e. Empathy: giving sincere and personal attention to customers, this is done to determine consumer desires accurately and specifically.

Revisiting Interest

The word interest comes from English namely *interest*, which means the urge to behave in a concrete direction towards the object of a particular activity or experience, so that the interest

in a return visit is the urge of someone to make a return visit to a destination that was visited [11]. The theory of *reasoned action and planned behavior* is the model, most often used to predict a behavior since the early 1980s. The desire to travel in the future is influenced by their attitude towards their past experiences. There are several factors that affect the interest of revisiting, namely [6]:

1. Service Quality: the impression of the quality of service, received by tourists, will affect the behavior of tourists who come. The more satisfying the quality of the services, provided by the service provider, the greater interest in coming back.

2. Destination Image: awards, obtained by tourism objects because of the advantages, possessed by tourism objects, can affect the interest of visiting again. The better the destination image, the greater the interest in revisiting.

3. Travel Attractions: things that attract tourists to visit a tourist object affect the interest of tourists to visit again. The better the attraction of a tourist object, the greater the interest in coming back.

4. Promotion: serves to create an image or impression of what is advertised. The better the promotion, the more attractive the tourists will be to visit again.

4. Conclusion

The regional tourism industry is related to the duties and functions of the promotion section and the quality of services in planning and implementing strategies to optimize the interest of returning tourists by promoting tourism services for tourist attraction locations to attract tourists and investors to the relevant institution or agency. The quality of service within these institutions and local governments in the field of tourism is very closely related and has a strong influence on the tourism industry. In this connection, there are important promotion and service quality factors, related to the interest of tourist return visits that involve the politics of a region's government which directly and indirectly influences the growth and development of the region's tourism industry. Directly, there is the attitude of the local government towards tourist visits both domestic and foreign, and indirectly namely the existence of stable situations and conditions in the political, economic and security developments in the region itself. Promotion and publicity in tourism play an important role in developing human civilization by highlighting the moral, cultural, social, ethical, educational, and psychological aspects of the public in a region. Tourism promotion and publicity planning is based on the best possible basis of communication, strategy, tactics and techniques.

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